

A MARINE FORECASTER'S VIEW OF PRESENT OCEAN WEATHER DATA TECHNOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

The present state of marine weather data technology may be broken down into two major categories: 1) "in-situ" environmental measurements; and 2) remote sensing of the marine environment.

In-situ weather measurements are routinely taken by observers on cooperating commercial vessels and aircraft crossing the oceans, as well as on the few remaining ocean weather station vessels. To an increasing extent however, observations of surface weather are being taken by automated buoys of several types. Coastal winds and waves are being observed by automated recording devices along the U.S. coastline.

Remote sensing from operational satellites has also become an important source of data. Meteorological and surface oceanographic data is now available in real-time on a routine basis from several satellite systems, and development is continuing on new and improved types of sensors. Land-based remote sensors, particularly involving microwave applications, also show great promise for the near future.

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, both gains and losses have been realized in the acquisition and use of real-time marine weather data. The losses have come in the form of cutbacks in human observational elements, such as permanently located ocean weather ships and coastal observing stations. The gains in data acquisition have resulted from rapid advances in automation technology in a number of fields. While every effort is being made to retain human observations (such as synoptic observations from commercial vessels), the major portion of currently available time and resources is being expended in the development of automated systems.

The authors are involved on a day-to-day basis with real-time marine weather and oceanographic data in support of routine as well as specialized marine weather forecasting. This paper is thus offered as a view of present technology from the user's, rather than the engineer's or researcher's,

perspective.

II. IN-SITU MEASUREMENTS

A. Ocean-going Vessels

Ocean-going vessels have long been used by the National Weather Service to take observations in the vast areas of the globe covered by water. Normally barographs, psychrometers, and wind equipment are placed aboard cooperating ships of opportunity and government vessels. Observations are taken once every six hours, at 0000, 0600, 1200, and 1800 GMT, which are worldwide standard weather observing times. They also correspond to the twice-daily release of upper air balloons around the world at 0000 and 1200 GMT. Normal procedure is for these observations to be transmitted in Morse code by the ship's radio operator to land-based Coast Guard or commercial stations. From there they are relayed via teletype to the National Meteorological Center in Washington, D.C., where they are compiled, and surface analyses are prepared, using a combination of these ship reports and land reports. Information from satellite images is used to fill in the areal gaps in the data for placement of fronts and storm centers.

B. Ocean Station Vessels

Ship reports provide a glimpse of what is happening at the surface, but the movement of weather systems is quite often determined by the steering winds aloft, from 10,000 to 40,000 feet. This is where the radiosonde balloons that are released every day prove invaluable. Unfortunately, several ships that used to be manned by weather observers, whose primary purposes were to take surface observations and release and track balloons, have met their demise due to the high cost of ship maintenance and the escalating salaries of the personnel. Only one ocean station, Ship Papa, is still manned in the Pacific on a year-round basis, and the Canadian government is planning to phase it out in the next two years. Europe fares a little better than North America, as there are four ocean stations in the Atlantic, with one each manned by the United Kingdom, France, Norway, and the USSR. The United States, by contrast, has pulled all of its weather ships out of the Atlantic, as well as the Pacific (seven in all). The reasoning given was that satellite data would

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replace these reports. Unfortunately, the development of indirect satellite observation technology did not keep pace with expectations.

C. Automated Buoys

A continuing problem with ship reports is that ships have a tendency to steer away from large or intense storm systems. This avoidance of the storm centers, along with the fact that ship reports quite frequently are bunched together along the shipping lanes, leaving large data-sparse areas, can be frustrating to the weather forecaster. One partial solution to this lack-of-data problem has been the development of instrumented, deep ocean moored buoys, which have been placed at strategic locations in the waters that surround North America (Figure 1).

Figure 1. North Pacific environmental buoy locations. Solid circles indicate buoys presently in operation. Open circles are planned locations. Solid triangle shows location of Ship Papa.

Presently, there are several different configurations to the buoys. These include both 10 meter and 12 meter discus-shaped hulls, as well as a 6 meter NOMAD Buoy, which is shaped like a ship's hull. The meteorological instruments are mounted on a tower either 5 or 10 meters high. There are duplicate instruments for measuring wind speed and direction, atmospheric pressure, and air and sea temperatures. See Figure 2.

Sea state is the element subject to the widest variation among reports from human observers. Significant wave height and period, and wave spectral energies from the buoys are all standardized, using accelerometers, so changes from one observation to the next are due to environmental changes, rather than caused by an observer watch change.

Figure 2. Twelve meter discus-hull environmental buoy. (Courtesy of NDBO)

The buoys derive power for the instrumentation from batteries located inside the hull. They are designed to operate over two years between replacements. However, a service trip is normally scheduled to each buoy every summer.

When the buoys were first placed, communication was handled by interrogating them from a shore station via HF radio. Now this has changed to interrogation thru the weather satellites (GOES) located above the equator. The information is then transmitted to the tracking station at Wallops Island, Virginia, and sent directly to the National Meteorological Center in Washington, D.C., where it is processed and relayed to weather forecast offices.

In addition to these buoys located hundreds of miles out at sea, the NOAA Data Buoy Office (NDBO) recently instrumented the Coast Guard's Large Navigational Buoy (LNB) that was placed at the entrance to the mouth of the Columbia River. Preliminary results have been satisfactory, so additional sites will likely be instrumented in the future. This instrumentation was done to replace observations from the Columbia River Lightship, which was retired at the end of October, 1979.

Two other types of buoys that are used by forecasters are wave-rider and drifting buoys. Wave-riders are tethered to a moored buoy and are frequently used for short periods of time. Their most popular use is for calibrating other wave-measuring instrumentation. An accelerometer within the buoy measures the wave motion and converts it to wave height and period. One variety transmits signals directly to the GOES satellite for relay to the Wallops Island tracking station. Another variety beams a continuous VHF signal from its antenna to a recording device either located on board a nearby ship or at a shore station. Here the information is either converted to height values every one-half second, or is traced on a chart strip recorder.

Drifting buoys have the advantage of being deployed either by ship or by airplane, so they can be placed over large areas of the ocean. The ones now in place in the South Pacific measure sea surface temperature and barometric pressure, and are interrogated by the TIROS/NOAA Polar Orbiting Satellites. The data is stored on board the satellite until it receives a command to release the data as it passes over a tracking station.

D. Automated Fixed Wavemeters

West Coast marine forecasters have information available from two automated coastal wave monitoring systems currently in operation, one being employed along the Pacific Northwest coast and the other along the California coast.

The system in use along the Washington-Oregon coast consists of specially designed seismic wavemeters, built and installed by Oregon State University at eight major harbor entrances. These wavemeters operate on the principle that waves incident to a sloping beach will be partially reflected, causing the formation of standing waves. Such standing waves in turn produce a pressure field on the bottom which generates seismic ground waves that are detectable some distance away (Reference 1). The seismometers are located in Coast Guard stations (all within one to two kilometers of the beach), and have direct readouts visible to the watchstanders at each station. (A sample chart strip record is shown in Figure 3.) Wave height and period are included in three-hourly weather observations sent from these stations to the National Weather Service. In addition, wave height and period from two of the stations (Cape Disappointment and Westport) are available at any time via interrogation through a remote terminal.

Along the California coast, a series of approximately twenty wavemeters is being established by the Scripps Institution of Oceanography, and

communications are being set up to make measurements available to the National Weather Service. These wavemeters include pressure transducers located on piers or on the ocean bottom, and also some wave-rider buoys. Wave spectra will be available from these instruments through interface with the Scripps computer.

No real-time automated wave observations are currently available on the East Coast or in the Gulf of Mexico, although some programs involving wave-rider buoys and oil drilling platforms are expected to be instituted soon.

E. Aircraft

In addition to wind, cloud, and free air temperature reports received from regularly scheduled airlines and private pilots, the government sends up heavily-instrumented aircraft to observe special weather situations. The most well-known of these are the hurricane reconnaissance flights from Miami. These planes fly into the eye of tropical storms and hurricanes to get a definite fix on their locations and to measure pressure, air temperature, dew point, and, using their inertial navigation system, wind direction and speed. In the Pacific Northwest, military planes routinely fly into approaching weather systems to determine their severity and speed of movement.

F. Automated Coastal Weather Stations

Coast Guard stations along the coast have traditionally provided weather observations to the data network. However, because of budgetary controls and reallocation of resources, more and more isolated lighthouses and stations are being automated. The National Weather Service, in cooperation with other agencies and academic institutions, has tried to fill these gaps by installing automated sensors. For example, Oregon State University has set up sensors for measuring sea and air temperatures along the Washington-Oregon coast, while the National Weather Service has

Figure 3. Sample seismic wavemeter trace. Displacements on either side of zero represent total wave height (not wave amplitude or displacement from mean water level). Significant wave height for this eight minute period is about 6 to 8 ft. (Courtesy of Clayton Creech, OSU Marine Science Center.)

installed several DARDC systems (Device for Automatic Remote Data Collection), which measure wind speed and direction at a number of coastal locations. Several different types of wind equipment have been field-tested in these DARDC's, but currently the F-420 wind system, in use at thousands of airports and weather offices around the country, is proving the most reliable. This equipment is especially useful on remote islands off the coast where winds are not obstructed by mountains, trees, or buildings. Data from DARDC locations is collected through the Coast Guard microwave relay system, and is accessible to marine forecasters via remote data terminals. Some DARDC's are also connected to the Coast Guard's remote visibility sensor, which automatically turns on a fog horn when visibility is restricted. This instrument consists of a device that measures backscatter from a strobe light.

III. OPERATIONAL REMOTE SENSING

A. Satellites

Since the first photograph of cloud cover from space was taken, over twenty years ago, great advances have been made in the field of satellite monitoring of the atmospheric and oceanic environment. Today, civilian meteorologists and oceanographers have data available from two separate satellite systems in real-time.

The first of these systems is known as the Geostationary Operational Environmental Satellite (GOES) system. For coverage over the United States, data is obtained from two spacecraft. These are in circular orbits at altitudes of about 35,800 km and travel at about 11,000 km/hr. At this particular altitude and speed, they revolve around the earth at the same rate as the earth rotates, the net effect being that the satellites remain continuously over the same points on earth. This type of orbit is termed geostationary or geosynchronous. The two GOES satellites covering the United States are placed over the equator at longitudes of 75°W and 135°W, and provide overlapping coverage over most of the country, while also having the capability of covering much of the Pacific and Atlantic Oceans.

The primary instrument on the GOES satellite producing imagery for marine forecasting is known as the Visible and Infrared Spin Scan Radiometer (VISSR), which provides visible data at 0.8 km resolution and infrared data at 8 km resolution (at the satellite sub-point). The VISSR data from both satellites is processed at the NOAA Central Data Distribution Facility (CDDF) near Washington, D.C., and then transmitted throughout the country. Visible data may be "sectorized", or split into specified geographical areas with resolutions of 0.9, 1.9, and 3.7 km. The CDDF can also sectorize infrared imagery to provide coverage of the same geographical areas as the visible sectors for 1.9 and 3.7 km resolutions. Infrared imagery may be temperature-enhanced for emphasis of specific features such as cloud tops. All images are automatically geographically gridded. National Weather Service Forecast Offices around the country

Figure 4. Sample GOES visible image.

receive these images every thirty minutes around the clock, and most offices choose to receive a variety of infrared and visible images at various resolutions over their area of interest. (See Figure 4.)

The second major satellite system used operationally by marine forecasters is known as the TIROS-N/NOAA series of polar orbiting satellites. At present, two satellites from this series, known as TIROS-N and NOAA-6, are in orbit. These satellites are in sun-synchronous (local equator crossing the same local time each day) orbits which pass nearly over the poles. They fly at an altitude of 833 to 854 km (much lower than GOES) and have an orbital period of about 100 minutes. Figure 5 is a depiction of the TIROS-N spacecraft.

These satellites have several instrument systems on board, employing visible, infrared, and microwave sensors. The two most important for marine weather purposes are: 1) the TIROS Operational Vertical Sounder (TOVS), which uses infrared and microwave sensors to make measurements of temperature and moisture profiles in the atmosphere; and 2) the Advanced Very High Resolution Radiometer (AVHRR), which produces visible and infrared imagery in four spectral channels at 1 km resolution. TOVS data is used as input into the advanced numerical models which produce prognostic charts of future weather for use by forecasters. AVHRR data is used to show location of weather systems, sea ice, and sea surface temperatures, when properly enhanced in the infrared channels. The latter capability is presently in use in global sea-surface temperature mapping, as well as for location of important features such as ocean currents (Gulf Stream, etc.) and coastal upwelling. Figure 6 is an AVHRR image from TIROS-N.

In addition to the NOAA satellite systems just described, the Department of Defense operates a sophisticated system of environmental satellites

Figure 5. Depiction of TIROS-N spacecraft. (Courtesy of W. John Hussey)

known as the Defense Meteorological Satellite Program (DMSP), which is used by forecasters in the U.S. military. However, this data is not routinely available to civilian agencies, and will not be described here.

B. Microwave Applications

Operational applications of microwave remote sensing have been limited thus far, although a great deal of developmental work is in progress in this field, and experimental results show great promise (see section IV).

As mentioned previously, the TOVS system on the TIROS-N/NOAA satellite series employs a microwave sensor as part of its instrument package. This instrument is sensitive in the oxygen region of the microwave spectrum, and has the unique ability to take measurements through clouds.

A second microwave instrument which has been used operationally (and concurrently in a testing-evaluation mode) is a radar altimeter flown on a NASA-operated satellite known as the Geodynamics Experimental Ocean Satellite (GEOS-3). This satellite had the capability of deriving significant wave height using waveform return from a narrow-pulse radar. In addition, techniques were developed to derive surface wind speeds from microwave backscatter data. Several NWS Forecast Offices had access to this data daily in real-time for approximately a six-month period in 1978, until the instrument's failure. The data was found to contain some biases, but was nevertheless particularly useful in open ocean areas where ship observations are sparse. This type of instrument is an integral part of proposed future operational ocean environmental satellites (see Section IV).

Imaging radar systems on civilian and military research aircraft have been used occasionally for special purposes, such as sea ice concentration

Figure 6. TIROS-N AVHRR image. Note open cellular clouds offshore, and light shades indicating colder water right along the California coast.

measurements and ocean wave and current studies. In some cases, data from these flights has been made available in near real-time to forecasters, but is not regular or cost-effective enough to be relied upon in an operational sense.

IV. FUTURE OUTLOOK

A. Buoy Advancements

Several ideas that are on the drawing board or are being tested now include peak wind gust measurement, directional wave spectra, and the Aids to Navigation Buoy Environmental Sensing System (ANBESS). Peak wind gusts are now being measured aboard several of the deep ocean moored buoys. A major problem is that there is presently no accepted meteorological code for transmitting this information. Hopefully, the World Meteorological Organization will revise the synoptic ship and buoy code in the 1980s to accommodate this parameter.

Another system presently undergoing testing by the NOAA Data Buoy Office (NDBO) is a method for determining directional wave spectra. Data is acquired using a heave sensor and a pitch/roll sensor. Dissemination to the users will likely consist of addition of wave direction for each frequency band to the present one-dimensional spectral reports (Reference 2).

In the ANBESS system, NDBO proposes to instrument many of the Coast Guard coastal buoys with meteorological equipment for measuring wind speed and direction and air and sea-surface temperatures. The data would be collected by satellite interrogation.

B. Satellite Developments

In addition to various evolutionary refinements in the GOES and TIROS-N/NOAA series satellites, several new applications will be instituted in

the next decade. During its three months of operation in 1978, the experimental ocean satellite known as Seasat performed a wide variety of tests on various sensors in a proof-of-concept mission for future operational satellites. The primary new program currently under development is a cooperative venture between NOAA, NASA, and the Department of Defense, and is known as the National Oceanic Satellite System (NOSS). Now in the planning and contracting stages, the system is expected to become operational in 1985. Several of the instruments tested on Seasat will be part of the NOSS package. Many of these involve the use of microwave radar. Following is a brief description of some of the major instruments:

(1) Radar altimeter - This instrument is an active short-pulse radar directed only at nadir, which will be used to measure sea-surface elevations for geodetic purposes and for determination of significant wave height and wind speed. This will be essentially the same instrument that was flown on GEOS-3, described earlier.

(2) Scatterometer - This will be the primary instrument for measuring wind speed and direction. It is an active microwave radar which applies Bragg scattering principles to compute winds based on radar backscatter from wind-induced capillary ocean waves.

(3) Scanning Multi-channel Microwave Radiometer (SMMR) - This is a scanning passive radiometer which measures microwave radiation at several frequencies, and will be used for obtaining sea-surface temperatures, sea ice locations, and surface wind speeds (but not directions). The SMMR has an advantage over infrared instruments in that it is essentially unaffected by cloud cover. However, its resolution is much lower than that of infrared sensors.

(4) Visible and Infrared Radiometer - This is a more conventional type of radiometer which will measure earth radiation in visible and infrared wavelengths for cloud and sea-surface temperature mapping.

(5) Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) - This is a very high resolution imaging radar which uses Doppler effects of the moving spacecraft to artificially increase the effective antenna beam-width (and thus the resolution) of the radar. A spatial resolution of 25 meters is possible. The SAR will be used to measure wavelength and direction (possibly wave height in the future), and to observe such features as sea and lake ice, spilled oil, internal waves, and coastal processes.

(6) Coastal Zone Color Scanner (CZCS) - This is a special radiometer devoted to ocean color determination. It measures backscattered solar radiation in several visible and one infrared channel. Radiance measurements in these various channels can then be related to physical properties such as biopigment and suspended sediment concentrations.

It should be noted that two of the above instruments (SMMR & CZCS) are part of the instrument package on the experimental satellite, NIMBUS-7, currently in orbit. A limited operational use of NIMBUS-7 data in near real-time in support of the 1980 albacore fishery in the mid North Pacific is being planned through cooperation between NOAA, NASA, and the Navy.

C. Other Uses of Microwave Radar

All of the instruments mentioned in the preceding section could be deployed on aircraft as well as on orbiting spacecraft, and would, due to reduced altitude, provide a much higher resolution look at a particular area. To our knowledge, however, no regular operational usage of such instruments for the measurement of winds, ocean waves, water temperatures, etc., from aircraft are planned, due to high operating costs of routine flights.

The use of land-based radar units is highly probable, however. Much work has been done (see Reference 3) using shore-based imaging radar to provide a two-dimensional picture of the wave field on a conventional radar display. Determination of wave height is not possible, but incoming wave direction and wavelength is obtainable. Future deployment of a series of coastal radar units in conjunction with a network of wavemeters would provide forecasters with a complete real-time picture of the incoming wave field.

Shore-based radar can also be used to measure surface currents out to about 70 km in real-time (see Reference 4). This system, known as CODAR (Coastal Ocean Data Acquisition Radar), uses Doppler shifts in the Bragg scatter from ocean waves to determine the prevailing underlying current. This will be extremely useful in fisheries, oil spill, and climatic applications. Coastal radar measurements of ocean waves and currents are not routine at present. NOAA is engaged in the development and engineering of such systems for operational use in the 1980's.

Another new development is the use of land-based skywave radar to monitor ocean surface conditions at long distances (up to 4000 km). This has the capability of measuring wave height and non-directional wave spectra. Wind direction may also be inferred from the direction of movement of small gravity waves. Skywave radar will be especially important in obtaining surface measurements in hurricanes and intense oceanic extratropical storms, which ships often avoid, and for which little data is normally available. Real-time data from this system should be on-line within three years.

D. Automation of Shipboard Observations

A Shipboard Environmental Data Acquisition System (SEAS) program has been proposed. This would consist of a transmitting device located aboard a ship that would be automatically interrogated via the GOES Satellite. Currently, the radio operator sometimes has problems contacting a shore facility to pass on a weather message, or might be too busy performing other functions.

The SEAS device will hopefully eliminate these problems. It would be designed to accept both manual data such as present weather, visibility, and sea state, as well as being connected to sensors that could produce automatic readings, such as barometric pressure, temperature, and wind speed and direction.

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